

1 ROR2 is a lineage regulating factor active in TE commitment decisions.

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of ROR2 as a lineage commitment factor in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

8 Citations

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